

COMPARISON OF TAMED EULER AND ε -EULER-MARUYAMA FOR STOCHASTIC DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS WITH LÉVY NOISE

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Abstract

In this research we explore two numerical approaches for simulating the stochastic differential equations (SDEs) with Lévy noise. This study focus on a stochastic logistic equation (SLE) by two independent Lévy processes. The research assesses the Tamed Euler and ε -Euler-Maruyama methods, both method ware designe for SDEs with nonlinear coefficient. To measure their performance, two generally used error metrics—Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) are employed. Result shows that, the Tamed Euler scheme tends to produce more accurate approximations. Owing to, in cases involving strong noise and larger time step size, the ε -Euler-Maruyama method has better performace than Tamed approach. The investigation further examines how different parameters affect the precision and stability of each method. The results prove that both schemes are effective and suitable for numerically solving SDEs with Lévy noise.

Keywords: Stochastic differential equations, Lévy noise, Logistic growth model, Numerical solution.

Introduction

Ordinary differential equations (ODEs) have recently been broaden employed in modeling natural, social, and engineering phenomena 1-3. Nonetheless, many real-world systems are subject to random fluctuations and disturbances that cannot be captured by deterministic models. To address this limitation, stochastic differential equations (SDEs) have been stated as

tools for modeling such systems the incorporation of uncertainty and randomness into the analysis 4-6.

One of the popular models in population dynamics is the logistic growth model, which explains population growth by taking into account the environmental carrying capacity. In its classical form, the model is deterministic and is formulated as follows:

$$dX(t) = X(t) [r(t) - a(t)X(t)] dt \quad (1)$$

In this equation, $X(t)$ is the population size at time t , $r(t)$ represents the intrinsic growth rate and $a(t)$

is the competition coefficient (assuming the carrying capacity is $\frac{r}{a}$) 7-8.

Although this model is suitable for stable, noise-free conditions, real-world systems often experience random disturbances. To account for such fluctuations, stochastic noise is incorporated into the model 8.

In this study, we consider a SLE that includes both Brownian noise and Lévy noise. To achieve this, the following stochastic components are introduced into equation (1),(e.g 78):

$$r(t) = r + \sigma_1 \frac{dL_1}{dt}, \quad -a(t) = -a + \sigma_2 \frac{dL_2}{dt} \quad (2)$$

L_1 and L_2 are Lévy processes. By incorporating the above stochastic terms into equation (1), we obtain the following stochastic differential equation:

$$dX(t) = X(t) [(r - aX(t))dt + \sigma_1 dL_1 + \sigma_2 X(t) dL_2] \quad (3)$$

If dL_1 and dL_2 are Lévy processes with zero mean and small jumps. By applying the Lévy-Itô decomposition to incorporate these components, the following stochastic differential equation is obtained:

$$dX(t) = X(t) \left[(r - aX(t))dt + \sigma_1 dB_1 + \sigma_2 X(t) dB_2 + \sigma_1 \int_{|z|<1} z \tilde{N}_1(dt, dz) + \sigma_2 X(t) \int_{|z|<1} z \tilde{N}_2(dt, dz) \right] \quad (4)$$

In this formula:

- r is the intrinsic growth rate;
- a is the environmental carrying capacity coefficient;
- σ_1 and σ_2 are the noise intensity parameter;
- dB_1 and dB_2 are independent standard Wiener processes;
- $\tilde{N}_1(dt, dz)$ and $\tilde{N}_2(dt, dz)$ is a compensated Poisson random measure modeling small jumps in the

system 9.

In this model, continuous fluctuations are represented by Brownian motion, while sudden shocks or jumps are captured by the Lévy process. Unlike Brownian noise, which only models continuous variations, Lévy noise has the capacity to represent sudden and discontinuous jumps. As such, employing SDEs driven by Lévy noise in logistic models allows for a more realistic analysis of biological, economic, and social systems 1011.

Although analytical solutions to such equations are rarely available, numerical approximation is developed to address this challenge. In this paper, we employ two prominent numerical schemes to solve the SLE with Lévy noise, namely:

1. Tamed Euler Scheme

Consider the following stochastic differential equation:

$$dx_t = a_t(x_t)dt + b_t(x_t)dB_t + \int_Z \gamma_t(x_t, z)\tilde{N}(dt, dz) \tag{5}$$

Where:

- $a: \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ is the drift function,
- $b: \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d \times m}$ is the diffusion coefficient,
- $\gamma: \mathbb{R}^d \times Z \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ represents the jump size function (compensated Poisson term),
- B_t is an m-dimensional standard Brownian motion,
- $\tilde{N}(dt, dz)$ is the compensated Poisson random measure over the jump space 12.

To discretize this equation, the following scheme is used:

$$dx_t^n = a_t^n(x_{\kappa(n,t)}^n)dt + b_t^n(x_{\kappa(n,t)}^n)dB_t + \int_Z \gamma_t^n(x_{\kappa(n,t)}^n, z)\tilde{N}(dt, dz) \tag{6}$$

In this formulation, the functions $a_t^n(x)$ and $b_t^n(x)$ are measurable with respect to the σ -algebra $P \otimes B(\mathbb{R}^d)$, taking values in \mathbb{R}^d and $\mathbb{R}^{d \times m}$, respectively. Similarly, the jump coefficient $\gamma_t^n(x, z)$ is measurable with respect to $P \otimes B(\mathbb{R}^d) \otimes L$, and takes values in \mathbb{R}^d 1213. The functions $a_t^n(x_t^n)$ and $\kappa(n, t)$ are defined as follows:

$$\kappa(n, t) := \frac{\lfloor n(t-t_0) \rfloor}{n} + t_0, \quad b_t^n(x) = \frac{b_t(x)}{1 + n^{-\theta} |b_t(x)|}, \quad \theta \in \left(0, \frac{1}{2}\right) \tag{7}$$

2. The ε -Euler-Maruyama scheme

Consider the following stochastic differential equation:

$$X_t = X_0 + \int_0^t a(s, X_s)ds + \int_0^t b(s, X_s)dB_s + \int_0^t \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} c(s^-, X_{s^-}, z)(N(ds, dz) - \nu_s(dz)ds) \tag{8}$$

where $(B_t)_{t \geq 0}$ is a standard Brownian motion, and $N(dt, dz)$ is a Poisson random measure associated with the compensator $\nu_t(dz)dt$ 1415.

For each $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, let us define a uniform time partition of the interval $[0, T]$ as, $0 = t_0 < \dots < t_n = T$, with fixed step sizes. Assume that $(\xi_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ is a sequence of independent identically distributed (i.i.d.) standard Gaussian random variables, independent of the Brownian motion B_t and the Poisson random measure N . The ε -Euler-Maruyama discretization scheme for equation (5) is then given by 1415:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{X}_{t_i}^\varepsilon &= \bar{X}_{t_{i-1}}^\varepsilon + \left(a(t_{i-1}, \bar{X}_{t_{i-1}}^\varepsilon) - \int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_i} \int_{\square \setminus B(\varepsilon)} c(s, \bar{X}_{t_{i-1}}^\varepsilon, z)\nu_s(dz)ds \right) \frac{T}{n} \\ &+ b(t_{i-1}, \bar{X}_{t_{i-1}}^\varepsilon) \sqrt{\frac{T}{n}} (B_{t_i} - B_{t_{i-1}}) + \left(\int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_i} \int_{B(\varepsilon)} c^2(s, \bar{X}_{t_{i-1}}^\varepsilon, z)\nu_s(dz)ds \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \xi_i \\ &+ \sum_{j=N^\varepsilon(t_{i-1})+1}^{N^\varepsilon(t_i)} c(T^\varepsilon(j), \bar{X}_{t_{i-1}}^\varepsilon, Z^\varepsilon(j)) \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

The primary aim of this research is to compare the two numerical schemes for solving the SLE with Lévy noise, focusing on their accuracy, stability, and computational efficiency. The remainder of the study is organized as follows: introduction, main results, error analysis and conclusion.

Main Results

In this part, we numerically solved the equation (4) using the two previously described schemes. First, we obtain the numerical solution of the equation using the Tamed Euler method. The equation (4), when discretized via formula (6), takes the following form:

$$X_{k+1} = X_k + \frac{X_k(r - aX_k)}{1 + \left(\frac{\Delta t}{T}\right)^{\theta} |X_k(r - aX_k)|} + \sigma_1 X_k \Delta B_{1,k} + \sigma_2 X_k^2 \Delta B_{2,k} + \sigma_1 X_k \int_{|z|<1} z \tilde{N}_1(dt, dz) + \sigma_2 X_k^2 \int_{|z|<1} z \tilde{N}_2(dt, dz) \quad (10)$$

To generate the jumps, we get:

$$X_{k+1} = X_k + \frac{X_k(r - aX_k)}{1 + \left(\frac{\Delta t}{T}\right)^{\theta} |X_k(r - aX_k)|} + \sigma_1 X_k \Delta B_{1,k} + \sigma_2 X_k^2 \Delta B_{2,k} + \sigma_1 X_k \left(\sum_{j=1}^{P_{1,k}} Z_{1,j} - \lambda_1 E[Z_1] \right) + \sigma_2 X_k^2 \left(\sum_{j=1}^{P_{2,k}} Z_{2,j} - \lambda_2 E[Z_2] \right) \quad (11)$$

This is the discretized form of equation (4): in which Z_i denotes the jump sizes, $\Delta B_{i,k} \sim N(0, \Delta t)$ represents independent Brownian steps, $p_{i,k}$ is the number of jumps of N_i in the interval $[t_k, t_{k+1}]$, and $E[Z_i]$ is the mean jump size.

Similarly, the solution of the logistic equation (4) using the ε -Euler–Maruyama method (9) is given as follows:

$$X_{k+1} = X_k + X_k \left[(r - aX_k) \Delta t + \sqrt{\Delta t} (\sigma_1 \Delta B_{1,k} + \sigma_2 X_k \Delta B_{2,k}) + \sigma_1 \left(\int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_i} \int_{|z|<1} z^2 v_1(dz) ds \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \xi_{1,i} + \sigma_2 X_k \left(\int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_i} \int_{|z|<1} z^2 v_2(dz) ds \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \xi_{2,i} \right] \quad (12)$$

Equations (11) and (12) can be implemented directly in Python or MATLAB. Of course, in equation (12) the jump terms are modeled using the Gaussian distribution.

Error Analysis

without an exact analytical solution for the equation, assess the error of the proposed numerical methods by comparing them with a reference solution obtained using a finer time discretization. Additionally, we evaluate the error of each method with respect to the drift component of the equation. To this end, two types of errors are considered:

(1) Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and (2) Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

By analyzing the error with respect to the reference solution. For this purpose, consider the following initial parameter values as shown in the tables below.

Table1

States for initial values for capacity and initial size.

Initial Value	Value
X_0	1.0
Carrying Capacity $\frac{r}{a}$	5

The parameters used in the simulations are summarized in the following table;

Table2

State for growth rate, the environmental carrying capacity coefficient and noise intensity.

Parameter	Value
r	0.5
a	0.1
σ_1	0.05
σ_2	0.01
Poisson jump intensity	10
Gaussian jump intensity parameter	5

Given the above parameter values, the solution of the SLE (4) is as follows:

Figure 1: The trajectory of Eq (4) via Tamed Euler schem for different step size namely: $\Delta t = 1000$ (red path) and $\Delta t = 100000$ (black path)

Figure 2: The trajectory of Eq (4) via ϵ -Euler-Maruyama schem for different step size namely: $\Delta t = 1000$ (blue path) and $\Delta t = 100000$ (black path)

The mean absolute error (MAE) and the root mean square error (RMSE) are given as follows:

Table 3

MAE and RMSE Tamed Euler and ϵ -Euler-Maruyama method		
Type of Error	Tamed Euler	ϵ -Euler-Maruyama
MAE	0.76390	0.88876
RMSE	0.95057	1.0809

Now, using the same parameter values as before, but instead of computing the error with respect to the reference solution, we compare it against the solution of the drift-only component. The corresponding results are as follows:

Figure 3:

The trajectory of Eq (4) via Tamed Euler schema for $\Delta t = 1000$ (red path) and simple path the drift of Eq (4).

Figure 4: The trajectory of Eq (4) via ϵ -Euler-Maruyama schema for $\Delta t = 1000$ (blue path) and simple path the drift of Eq (4).

The corresponding error in this case is expressed as follows:

Table 3

MAE and RMSE Tamed Euler and ϵ -Euler-Maruyama against the drift of Eq (4)

Type of Error	Tamed Euler	ϵ -Euler-Maruyama
MAE	0.50124	0.57445
RMSE	0.63046	0.70913

Parameter Analysis in the Numerical Stability of the Solution

To compare better the performance of the two methods, evaluate them under various parameter settings.

Table 4

MAE and RMSE Tamed Euler and ε -Euler-Maruyama for different parameter.

T	X_0	Δt	$\frac{r}{a}$	σ_1	σ_2	Tamed Euler MAE	Tamed Euler RMSE	$\varepsilon - EM$ MAE	$\varepsilon - EM$ RMSE
1	1	0.1	5	0.05	0.01	0.071420	0.100933	0.122625	0.132886
	1	0.1	10	0.5	0.1	0.618594	0.854839	1.945907	2.119333
	1	0.01	5	0.05	0.01	0.052726	0.070615	0.085437	0.112624
	1	0.01	10	0.5	0.1	0.459237	0.621048	0.810467	1.115371
	1	0.01	15	0.5	0.1	0.532415	0.740914	1.080447	1.572890
	10	0.1	5	0.05	0.01	0.791203	1.149369	0.906782	1.103699
	10	0.1	10	0.5	0.1	2.193207	2.610637	3.829856	5.203263
	10	0.01	5	0.05	0.01	0.574412	0.718239	1.055213	1.234571
	10	0.01	10	0.5	0.1	3.121472	4.002206	4.031628	4.938707
	10	0.01	15	0.5	0.1	3.814062	4.437470	4.465705	5.368775
	100	0.1	5	0.05	0.01	12.94635	15.262922	8.582180	11.74682
	100	0.1	10	0.5	0.1	unstable	unstable	11.778112	39.06357
	100	0.01	5	0.05	0.01	31.74584	42.953933	9.071633	17.61709
	100	0.01	10	0.5	0.1	3.102545	5.493761	unstable	unstable
	100	0.01	15	0.5	0.1	3.162008	5.573845	unstable	unstable
	150	0.1	5	0.05	0.01	14.63128	16.161557	20.180123	23.65049
	150	0.1	10	0.5	0.1	unstable	unstable	26.120765	86.63277
	150	0.01	5	0.05	0.01	36.52442	66.428839	12.651398	32.40779
	150	0.01	10	0.5	0.1	3.688183	6.848950	unstable	unstable
	150	0.01	15	0.5	0.1	3.796851	7.031334	unstable	unstable
500	0.1	5	0.05	0.01	unstable	unstable	20.753472	24.49870	
500	0.1	10	0.5	0.1	unstable	unstable	284.31979	942.9820	
500	0.01	5	0.05	0.01	33.99907	66.915892	39.940050	121.8697	
500	0.01	10	0.5	0.1	0.398423	4.004102	6.721223	14.48594	
500	0.01	15	0.5	0.1	0.398499	4.004865	7.119608	14.63970	
100	500	0.1	5	0.05	0.01	2.837142	89.763151	5.065269	5.591503
	500	0.1	10	0.5	0.1	23.90431	756.29851	unstable	unstable
	500	0.01	5	0.05	0.01	5.524618	13.775567	5.127124	6.910637
	500	0.01	10	0.5	0.1	0.057900	1.431501	unstable	unstable
	500	0.01	15	0.5	0.1	0.058741	1.443803	unstable	unstable
	500	0.1	200	0.1	0.05	12.22173	386.67840	unstable	unstable
	500	0.1	200	0.5	0.1	23.90431	756.29859	unstable	unstable
	500	0.01	200	0.9	0.15	unstable	unstable	unstable	unstable
	500	0.01	200	1.4	0.2	unstable	unstable	unstable	unstable
	500	0.01	200	1.9	0.25	unstable	unstable	unstable	unstable
	500	0.01	200	0.1	0.05	0.052842	2.643326	unstable	unstable
	500	0.001	200	0.5	0.1	0.232985	4.144595	unstable	unstable
500	0.0001	200	1.9	0.25	0.127088	2.866097	0.002153	2.152705	

The above table is prepared for various parameter settings. As shown in the table, the numerical error of the Tamed Euler method is generally lower than that of the ε -Euler-Maruyama scheme. Under conditions of high noise intensity and large time steps, the ε -Euler-Maruyama method exhibits greater numerical instability compared to the Tamed Euler scheme. However, when the noise intensity is high and the time step is small, the ε -Euler-Maruyama method performs better.

Another important point to consider when comparing these two methods is computational cost. The Tamed Euler method is more time-consuming than the ε -Euler-Maruyama method.

Conclusion

SDEs with Lévy noise are particularly useful for modeling natural phenomena—especially population growth models. Since, such equations typically lack closed-form analytical solutions, numerical methods have been developed to approximate their solutions. This study presented and implemented an algorithm for solving SLE involving two Lévy noise components, demonstrating its effectiveness through practical computation.

The obtained error results confirm the accuracy of both methods under study. An important finding is that the Tamed Euler method prevents numerical explosion due to its modified drift term. In particular, it produces smaller errors rather than the ε -Euler-Maruyama method when larger time steps are used. Therefore, it is a suitable numerical approach for solving SDEs with super-linear drift terms.

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